

The Person behind Dyadic Communication. Exploring Leibniz's Monads, Dyadic Communication Measurement and The Quantum Observer Effect.

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Abstract:

This theoretical article provides insight into the concept of Person behind Dyadic communication, starting from the well-known Leibniz's theory of monads as self-contained and autonomous entities.

Leibniz's theory of monads represents a complex and innovative attempt to reconcile the principles of rationalism, metaphysics, and theology. Even though his conception of monads has faced criticism and debate, it remains a significant contribution to the history of philosophy and continues to inspire scholarly inquiry and interpretation. For example, this article will also offer an exemplification for teaching purposes, illustrating monads in society as cells immersed in interstitial liquid.

On the other hand, dyadic communication highlights the dynamic and interdependent nature of human interaction, where meaning is co-constructed through mutual engagement and exchange.

This paper will analyse the implications of monadology for the perception of individual identity and isolation, with its philosophical perspectives on relationality (Philosophy of Relational Existence), and discuss the nature of existence and subjectivity intersect with interpersonal dynamics. The transition from Leibniz's monads to dyadic communication reflects a broader shift from a metaphysical framework focused on isolated substances to a relational perspective highlighting interaction and communication between entities.

Furthermore, this article, in an unusual and at least daring attempt at interdisciplinary comparison between this philosophical background and the Subnuclear Physics Theory of Quantum Mechanics (Einstein, Heisenberg, et al.), in conjunction with the theory of the Pygmalion Effect of Rosenthal, will try to explain the methodological difficulties of the analytical measurement of this form of communication. It will conclude with the role of philosophy in sociological research.

1. Leibniz's Monads:

"La Monade, dont nous parlons ici, n'est autre chose qu'une substance simple qui entre dans les composés; simple c'est-à-dire sans parties." (Monadologie, 1)

In 1714, Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz (1646-1716) wrote *La Monadologie* (in English *The Monadology*¹), a concise text of only 90 paragraphs, in which he introduced the concept of monads², indivisible, unextended, and autonomous substances that are the fundamental building blocks of reality. Each monad is a self-contained entity with its unique perspective and internal states, which do not interact causally with one another, but they harmonise with each other. Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz's theory of monads is a central aspect of his metaphysical system. Here are some key points to consider when discussing Leibniz's theory of monads:

1. **Indivisibility and Unity:** According to Leibniz, monads are indivisible entities that cannot be decomposed into smaller parts. Each monad is a complete and self-contained substance that possesses its unique properties and qualities. Monads are characterised by their internal unity and coherence, distinguishing them from materialistic theories' composite substances.

¹ In this article I will refer to the original text, available at *Athena* from the University of Genève, and to the English translation by Robert Latta (1898), Oxford University.

² In philosophy, something of an individual substance, ultimate and indivisible. Leibniz was not the first to use this word nor this concept. It already appears in Pythagora, Aristotle, Plato, and others. For instance, the concept of monads can be found implicitly in the cosmological and metaphysical thought of Giordano Bruno. In his writings, such as 'De l'infinito, universo e mondi' (1576) and 'De gli eroici furori' (1585), Bruno dealt with the nature of the universe, its infinity and the unity of all things, as an infinite set of animate and living realities, all interconnected and interdependent. Although he does not explicitly use the term 'monads', his conceptions of the indivisible unity, eternity and vitality of the realities of the universe can be seen as precursors of similar concepts.

2. **Uniqueness and Pre-Established Harmony:** Leibniz argued that each monad is ontologically distinct from all others, possessing its unique perspective and internal states. Despite their individuality, monads are harmoniously interconnected through a pre-established harmony established by God³. This harmony ensures that the perceptions and experiences of different monads correspond with one another despite their ontological separateness.
3. **Perception and Appetition:** Leibniz proposed that monads are characterised by two primary faculties: perception and appetition. Perception refers to the capacity of monads to represent and apprehend external and internal states, while appetition denotes their inherent striving or tendency towards perfection and fulfilment. These faculties govern the dynamic unfolding of monadic existence as they guide the development and evolution of each monad's internal states.
4. **Windowless Monads and the Principle of Sufficient Reason:** Leibniz famously described monads as "windowless" entities, meaning they do not interact causally. In particular, each monad reflects the entire universe from its unique perspective without directly influencing or being influenced by other monads. This conception of monadic isolation is grounded in Leibniz's principle of sufficient reason, which posits that every event or phenomenon has a sufficient reason or explanation that can be traced back to the nature of individual substances.

³ Leibniz posits that God is the supreme monad, The Monad of Monads, as Synesius said. God is considered the highest and most perfect of all monads. Unlike created monads, which have limited perceptions, God's perceptions are infinite and encompass all possibilities, and he is the Creator and Sustainer of all other monads. God's will and understanding are perfect, and God's perceptions are clear and distinct, providing the ultimate basis for the pre-established harmony of the universe. He possesses infinite perfection, encompassing all power, knowledge, and goodness. As the source of all reality and the ultimate reason for everything that exists, God's nature as a monad is qualitatively different from that of created monads.

Leibniz's theory of monads has been subject to various critiques and interpretations throughout the history of philosophy. Critics have questioned the coherence of the concept of windowless monads and the mechanisms of pre-established harmony. Additionally, interpretations of Leibniz's monadology vary, with some scholars highlighting its theological implications and others focusing on its contributions to epistemology and metaphysics.

1.1. Monads and Person:

Indivisible, united and self-contained, unique and ontologically distinct from all others, harmoniously interconnected through a pre-established harmony that ensures that the perceptions and experiences of different monads correspond with one another, capable of representing and apprehending external and internal states while striving towards perfection and fulfilment, reflecting the entire universe from its unique perspective, without directly influencing or being influenced by others, living in "the best possible world." It is a Monad, but it sounds like a definition of "Person."

Leibniz's theory of monads has profound implications for the perception of individual identity and isolation. According to Leibniz, each monad is ontologically distinct from all others, possessing unique properties, qualities, and internal states; this implies that every individual entity, whether human or otherwise, has a different identity that sets it apart from all other entities. The concept of unique identity in monadology highlights each monad's individuality and specificity, highlighting the universe's richness and diversity.

When he famously described monads as "windowless" entities, meaning that they do not interact with one another causally, Leibniz pointed out that each monad reflects the entire universe from its unique perspective without directly influencing or being influenced by other monads. This notion of windowless isolation suggests a fundamental separateness and autonomy of individual entities, reinforcing the idea of self-contained identity.

Despite their ontological separateness, Leibniz proposed that monads are harmoniously interconnected through a pre-established harmony established by God⁴, making the world a cosmos, not a chaos.

This harmony ensures that the perceptions and experiences of different monads correspond with one another despite their individuality. While this concept suggests a degree of unity or coherence in the universe, it also implies a certain degree of isolation, as each monad exists within its unique sphere of perception and activity.

⁴ If the reader is looking for a more secular explanation of pre-determined harmony, or a non-theological interpretation to capture the essence of predetermined harmony - the idea that seemingly independent entities can exhibit some form of co-ordinated behaviour - without relying on a divine creator, it might be possible to rephrase the concept with a more secular understanding of how seemingly independent entities can exhibit some form of co-ordinated behaviour, such as:

- **Pre-Programmed Responses:** each monad (individual) has an internal code or set of rules that govern its responses to the world. These internal rules could be shaped by genetics, evolution, and past experiences.
- **Emergent Order from Independent Systems:** We could view harmony as an emergent property arising from the complex interactions of independent systems. Even though monads don't directly interact, their internal rules might lead to a form of synchronised behaviour, similar to how flocks of birds or schools of fish move in coordinated patterns.
- **Compatible Initial Conditions and Environmental Pressures:** Perhaps the initial state of each monad (influenced by genetics and environment) and the external pressures they encounter are inherently compatible. This compatibility could lead to a sense of harmony even without direct interaction.
- **Complexity Theory:** The field of complexity theory explores how simple rules governing individual entities can lead to complex emergent behaviour in systems.

But none of these are perfect replacements for the theological concept, because Leibniz's God played a crucial role in ensuring the harmony.

An **internal unity and coherence** govern each monad's existence and development. Leibniz proposed that monads possess an internal principle of activity or striving, known as **appetition**, which guides their actions and tendencies towards perfection and fulfilment. This internal unity contributes to the sense of individual identity and integrity within each monad despite its isolation from other entities. The perception of personal identity in monadology is closely tied to each monad's unique perspective and internal state. From Leibniz's perspective, individual identity is not merely a product of external relationships or interactions with other entities but arises from each monad's internal qualities and experiences. This perspective emphasises the subjective nature of identity and suggests that each individual entity perceives itself and its world from its unique vantage point.

The theory of monads presents a complex and nuanced understanding of individual identity and isolation, and it can be easily understood as a Theory of Person.

While each monad is ontologically distinct and isolated from others, it also participates in a harmonious unity (a Society?) that reflects the interconnectedness of the universe⁵. The perception of individual identity in monadology is shaped by each monad's unique perspective, internal states, and internal unity, highlighting the complexity and richness of personal existence.

⁵ See Annex A

2. Dyadic Communication

Dyadic communication⁶, as pointed out by Macionis and Gerber (2011), refers to a form of interpersonal, interactive communication between two entities or individuals as the smallest possible social group.

Unlike Leibniz's monads, which exist as isolated substances, dyadic communication implies a relational and interactive process involving two participants. Such relationships are usually based on equality⁷, but may also be based on an asymmetrical or hierarchical relationship, like in a master-servant. The time spent together and the emotional intensity of the relationship are used to assess the strength of the relationship.

This concept is based on the studies of George Simmel⁸ about Social Geometry (1908). In a dyad, one can retain individuality without fear that another may shift the group's balance.

⁶ Dyad means two things of a **similar kind** or nature or group, and dyadic communication means the relationship between the two. In practice, this relationship refers to dialogical relations or face-to-face verbal communication between two people, a lasting communication of ideas between two people for a long duration of time or of any intensive duration of deeper impact, involving their mutual ideas, thoughts, behaviour, ideals, likes, dislikes, and questions and answers about life and living in nature. A sudden communication between two strangers in the street that is not continued or has no lasting effect on each other cannot be called dyadic communication.

⁷ A dyad can be unstable because both persons must cooperate to make it work. If one of the two fails to complete their duties, the group would fall apart. Because of the significance of **marriages** in society, their stability is very important. For this reason marital dyads are often enforced through legal, economic, and religious laws.

⁸ George Simmel, Berlin 1858-1918, was influential in the field of sociology. According to "Biografie", (Georg Simmel Gesellschaft. www.simmel-gesellschaft.de. Retrieved 10 May 2024.) Simmel belonged to the first generation of German sociologists: his neo-Kantian approach laid the foundations for sociological antipositivism, asking "What is society?" - a direct allusion to Kant's "What is nature?" - and presenting pioneering analyses of social individuality and fragmentation. His PhD thesis had the title "The Nature of Matter According to Kant's Physical Monadology". Simmel discussed social and cultural phenomena in terms of "form" and "content", with a transient relationship in which form becomes content and vice versa, depending on the context. In this sense, Simmel was a forerunner of structuralist modes of argumentation in the social sciences. So doing, he pioneered the structuralist approach to social science. Simmel's work on the metropolis (1903, *Die Großstädte und das Geistesleben*, The metropolis and the mental Life) also foreshadowed urban sociology, symbolic interactionism and social network analysis. Simmel was a friend of Max Weber. The eclectic critical theory of the Frankfurt School would draw on both Simmel's and Weber's non-positivist theory.

In contrast, as pointed out by Zhang and Emery (2023), triads (i.e., three-person groups) risk the potential of one member becoming subordinate to the other two, thus threatening their individuality. Furthermore, if a triad lost a member, it would become a dyad.

The essential nature of this dyad-triad principle forms the essence of structures that form society. As a group increases, it becomes more isolated and segmented, whereby the individual becomes further separated from each member.

Simmel's sociology was concerned with relationships—especially interaction—and was thus known as a *methodological relationalist*⁹. This approach is based on the idea that interactions exist between everything.

2.1. Definition

Dyadic communication occurs between two persons for social facilitation, fulfilment, or exchange of ideas and information. The two people both bear the responsibility of a successful interaction. By understanding the dynamics and principles of dyadic communication, individuals can enhance their interpersonal skills and cultivate more fulfilling and productive interactions.

This interaction can take various forms, including verbal communication, non-verbal cues, and mutual understanding between individuals, with the following characteristics:

⁹ Relationalism is any theoretical position that gives importance to the relational nature of things. For relationalism, things exist and function only as relational entities. **Relationalism** may be contrasted with **relationalism**, which tends to highlight relations *per se*. Relationalism, in the broadest sense, applies to any system of thought that gives importance to the relational nature of reality. In relational sociology, relationalism is often contrasted with substantialism. While substantialism (also called substantialism) tends to view individuals as self-subsistent entities capable of social interaction, relationalism underscores the social human practices and the individual's transactional contexts and reciprocal relations. Emirbayer, Mustafa (1997) wrote the "Manifesto for a Relational Sociology", published in *The American Journal of Sociology*. 103 (2): 281–317. doi:10.1086/231209)

1. **Two Participants:** Dyadic communication involves two participants or individuals who mutually exchange meaningful messages. This interaction can occur in various contexts, including face-to-face conversations, but any technological-based medium could be used, considering the well-known differences between vocal, verbal, and non-verbal communication.
2. **Mutual Influence:** Both participants have the opportunity to influence and be influenced by each other. They engage in a dynamic process of sharing thoughts, ideas, feelings, and information, with each person responding to and reacting to the other's messages through a...
3. **Feedback:** Feedback plays a crucial role in dyadic communication, as it allows participants to monitor and adjust their messages based on the other person's responses. Feedback can be verbal or nonverbal and may include cues such as nods, gestures, facial expressions, or verbal affirmations.
4. **Interpersonal Dynamics:** Dyadic communication is shaped by various interpersonal dynamics, including relationship history, power dynamics, cultural norms, and communication styles. These dynamics influence the way individuals interact with each other and can impact the quality and effectiveness of communication.
5. **Conflict and Resolution:** Dyadic communication can also involve conflict and disagreement, as individuals may have differing opinions, goals, or interests.
6. **Relationship Building:** Dyadic communication is crucial in relationship building and maintenance. Through ongoing interactions, individuals develop rapport, trust, and

understanding with each other, strengthening their interpersonal connections and fostering intimacy.

7. **The Speaker-listener roles** are frequently alternated.
8. **The purpose** may range from casually purposive to highly purposive but generally informal.

According to De Vito¹⁰ (1991), there are four significant purposes of dyadic communication:

- Personal Discovery,
- Discovery of the Outside world,
- Establishing meaningful relationships and
- Changing attitudes and behaviours.

This kind of communication allows us to learn about ourselves and the person we are talking with. Our self-images are built; in the meantime, we gain information about the people, things, and events around us. From this perspective, dyadic communication is a fundamental aspect of human interaction, serving as the foundation for meaningful relationships, collaboration, and social exchange.

¹⁰ Notable scholars and theorists within the field of communication studies have contributed to our understanding of dyadic communication. Joseph DeVito is a prominent scholar in communication studies who has written extensively on interpersonal communication, including the dynamics of dyadic interactions and relationship development. But significant contribution came also from Irwin Altman and Dalmás Taylor, with their Social Penetration Theory, which explores the process of relationship development through self-disclosure and intimacy in interpersonal interactions, including dyadic communication (See also *The Onion Model*). Michael Roloff and Charles Berger are known for their research on the *Uncertainty Reduction Theory*, which examines how individuals seek to reduce uncertainty and increase predictability in initial interactions, such as dyadic communication encounters. Julia Wood is an influential scholar in the field of interpersonal communication, with contributions to theories on gender and communication, as well as nonverbal communication, which are relevant to dyadic interactions.

2.2. Comparing Monadic and Dyadic theories

While Leibniz's monads present a challenge to dyadic communication in a literal or superficial sense, exploring the concept through the lenses of psychology and sociology offers intriguing possibilities.

In both these theories, the concept of **Individual Identity** is well represented:

<p>Leibniz's theory of monads, which emphasises that individuals are self-contained entities with their internal states and perceptions that shape their communication behaviours and responses, emphasises each individual entity's unique identity and internal coherence.</p>	<p>Similarly, in dyadic communication, each participant brings their distinct perspective, experience, and identity to the interaction.</p>
<p>Leibniz proposed that each monad reflects the universe from its unique perspective, perception, and understanding.</p>	<p>Similarly, in dyadic communication, individuals perceive and interpret the world based on their subjective experiences and beliefs.</p>
<p>The concept of monads highlights the subjective nature of perception, highlighting how individuals construct their understanding of reality based on their internal states.</p>	<p>In dyadic communication, participants must navigate differences in perception and interpretation as they seek to understand each other's perspectives and meanings.</p>

In the broadest sense, they both facilitate personal discovery, discovering the outside world, building meaningful relationships, and changing attitudes and behaviours.

These individuals are living in a certain harmony through Interpersonal Interaction: while monads in Leibniz's metaphysical framework are windowless and do not directly interact with each other, they nevertheless live in a harmonious relationship and seek each other out with "perception and appetite"; on the other side, dyadic communication involves more direct interaction and

exchange of messages between two individuals; it highlights the dynamic interplay between individuals as they engage in reciprocal exchanges of thoughts, feelings, and emotions. Each participant in dyadic communication influences and is influenced by the other, reflecting a form of relational interaction that transcends the isolation of monads. In so doing, participants strive for mutual understanding and coherence in their interactions, seeking to establish rapport, trust, and shared meaning. While the monads underscore the uniqueness of individual identity, dyadic communication emphasises the potential for harmony and unity in interpersonal relationships.

Leibniz proposed monads as the basic units of reality. These windowless substances have internal representations of the universe but cannot directly interact with each other. Each monad has a unique perspective on the universe, living together in a "pre-established harmony;" this could be seen as a form of indirect communication, where the "code" for understanding the universe is embedded within each monad.

From a sociological perspective, the concept of monads could be used to explore how societies function despite the inherent limitations of communication. Shared cultural norms, symbols, and language could act as a bridge, allowing for indirect communication and social coordination.

The limitations of monadic communication highlight the importance of shared frameworks, active interpretation, and the role of social structures in facilitating understanding since communication is also a process of interpreting internal representations facilitated by shared cultural norms and social structures.

While Leibniz's concepts of monads and dyadic communication operate within different frameworks and contexts, they both offer insights into the complexities of individual identity,

interaction, and perception. By exploring the parallels between these concepts, we can deepen our understanding of the dynamic nature of human communication and interpersonal relationships.

2.3. Challenges of the metric Dyadic Data Analysis

The concept of dyadic communication after more than one century is still actual, and with the studies of Coromina et al. (2008) and Kennedy et al. (2015), it evolved into the definition of a duocentric social network, that is a type of social network composed of the combined network members of a dyad. The network consists of mutual, overlapping ties between members of the dyad and non-mutual ties. The impetus for this original conceptualization was a compromise between the two most commonly used social network analytical methods: egocentric network, as defined by Djomba et al. (2016), and sociocentric network analyses (Perkins et al., 2015).

In an egocentric network analysis, a singular individual, his or her network members, and (occasionally) the ties between those alters are the focal points of the analysis. On the other hand, the socio-centric network approach utilises a bounded group as the unit of analysis, examining all ties between actors in the group.

Kennedy et al. maintained this basic framework but redefined the concept as duocentric networks and suggested that information on the relatedness of ties in the network should be collected, and analysis can be made. In fact, the dyadic or duocentric network offers valuable

insights into relationships, but it comes with its own set of challenges and has a peculiar metric that has to be considered.

About measuring Dyadic Communication there are several challenges to measuring dyadic communication, such as:

1. **Non-independence:** Observations from one member of the dyad are not independent of the other because one's response is likely to influence the other. Statistical methods designed for independent data may not be suitable.
2. **Limited Sample Size:** Studies often involve a relatively small number of dyads, limiting the generalizability of findings and the power of statistical tests.
3. **Missing Data:** If one dyad member does not participate or their data is incomplete, the entire dyad's data may be unusable.
4. **Focus on Individual Effects:** Dyadic analysis can struggle to separate the unique contributions of each member from the overall relational effects.
5. **Measurement Challenges:** Measuring the quality or dynamics of communication within a dyad can be complex and subjective.
6. **Self-Reported Measures:** Questionnaires and surveys ask each dyad member to report their communication behaviours, satisfaction, or perceptions of the other person's communication style. These are easy to administer but can be susceptible to bias.

7. **Observational Methods:** Trained observers watch the dyad interact and code their communication behaviours, such as turn-taking, emotional expression, or nonverbal cues: This provides objective data but requires expertise and can be time-consuming.
8. **Physiological Measures:** Techniques like heart rate monitoring or brain scans can measure physiological responses during communication. These offer insights into emotional arousal but may not directly capture the content or quality of communication.
9. **Conversational Analysis:** Researchers analyse the actual transcripts of conversations between dyad members, focusing on linguistic features like word choice, sentence structure, or conversation patterns: this offers rich data but requires specialised skills and can be time-consuming.

On top of all these factors, we must consider that different Types of Dyadic Communication exist (De Vito, 1991): the type of communication we want to measure will influence the chosen method.

For example, and without claiming to be exhaustive, we could identify some common types, such as:

- Informative Communication: Exchanging information and facts.
- Affective Communication: Expressing emotions and feelings.
- Instrumental Communication: Negotiating, problem-solving, or achieving goals.
- Relational Communication: Building and maintaining the relationship itself.
- Conversational Openness: Willingness to share personal thoughts and feelings, like in the value share of Social penetration Theory.
- Confirmation: Verbally and nonverbally acknowledging and validating the other person.
- Criticism: Expressing disapproval while maintaining respect.

2.4. Linking Leibniz's Monads to Dyadic Data Analysis Problems

Leibniz's concept of monads presents some interesting challenges when considering dyadic communication and the problems associated with its analysis. Here is how they connect¹¹:

2.4.1. Monads and Non-Independence:

According to Leibniz, Monads are windowless entities with internal representations of the universe. There is no way to access another monad's internal representation directly; they cannot interact directly but experience a pre-established harmony. Translating this problem to Data Analysis, we observe that Dyadic data analysis struggles with non-independence, where responses from one person in a dyad are influenced by the other. If monads had no direct interaction, then analysing communication between them, also by changing their functional name to "dyad," would be impossible. However, Leibniz's concept of pre-established harmony suggests a form of indirect communication.

¹¹ Limitation: It's important to remember that applying Leibniz's monads literally to human communication has limitations. Monads is a philosophical concept also applicable to the concept of the Person, but human communication involves a level of direct interaction and shared experience that Leibniz's model doesn't fully capture. However, exploring the concept through this lens highlights the inherent challenges of understanding communication, particularly in close relationships. Just as we can only infer the internal states of monads, we can only approach communication within a dyad by analysing the outward expressions and reports of each individual.

Shifting to the Data Analysis challenge, we found that measuring the **quality** or the **dynamics** of communication within a dyad is difficult because we can only access each person's **subjective** experience (self-reports) or **external behaviours** (observations). We rely on self-reported data or observations, which can be both subjective and incomplete.

This difficulty resonates with the idea that dyadic data analysis attempts to understand **communication** by examining the (potentially influenced) **responses** of each **individual** monad (person) within the **dyad**. However, in so doing, it is accepting the consequences dictated by the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle. This principle states that specific pairs of physical properties, like position and momentum (Feelings and behaviours, Person and Dyad, quality or dynamic), cannot be simultaneously measured with arbitrary precision. Observation of one property affects the other.

2.4.2. Monads and Focus on Individual Effects:

Suppose we accept the concept of a predetermined harmony by a Supreme Entity. It is unclear how individual monads contribute to the overall harmony because their internal representations are shaped by this pre-established harmony rather than by their own experiences. Likewise, Dyadic analysis needs help to separate the unique communication styles of each person from the overall relational effects that emerge from their interaction. Just as it is difficult to disentangle the influence of pre-established harmony from individual monadic experiences, dyadic data analysis can need help to isolate how each person's communication style influences the overall dynamic of the dyad. The limitations of directly

accessing a monad's internal world mirror the challenges of directly measuring communication within a dyad.

2.5. Quantum Observer Effect

The "Observer Effect" in Quantum Mechanics, the discipline in Physics that describes the behaviours of atoms, electrons, photons, and other particles that make up atoms, refers to the concept that the act of observing or measuring a system can alter its state or behaviour, leading to different results compared to when the system is not observed.

In a fascinating interdisciplinary approach, it can be defined as the equivalent of the physics of the Rosenthal "Pygmalion Effect" in psychology: from a layman's perspective, they both state the same. When a system is under observation and aware of such observation, its behaviour will change.

The mere act of observing a system affects its state, and the act of measurement directly alters the system's behaviour.

Such a statement has a profound consequence not only in subnuclear physics but also in sociology, giving rise to the concept of "Social Superposition," which is outside the scope of this article but will be delved deeper into the conclusions.

Before the measurement, the particles exist in a superposition of states, but on observation, they collapse into a new unambiguous state. Such effects were further defined by the Copenhagen School, by Heisenberg and Bohr, with the "Heisenberg uncertainty principle": this principle states that specific pairs of physical properties, like position and momentum, cannot be simultaneously

measured with arbitrary precision. Observation of one property affects the others¹². For example, measuring the quality of communication will affect its dynamic and vice versa.

Dyadic Measurement is also challenged by the Rosenthal or Pygmalion Effect (Rosenthal, 1968), which in psychology refers to the phenomenon where expectations from observers (e.g., teachers) lead to a change in performance in the observed subjects (e.g., students), in a kind of Expectation Influence or Self-fulfilling prophecy, where the expectations set by observers can influence the behaviour of subjects in such a way that the expected outcome is more likely to occur. In other words, the behaviour of individuals can change based on their awareness of being observed and the expectations tied to that observation.

Positive expectations lead to positive changes in performance.

In both examples, the quantistic or the psychological, awareness of observation plays a critical role. In quantum mechanics, the system "responds" to measurement, while individuals respond to perceived expectations in psychology. However, both effects show that the behaviour or state of the system under observation is not independent of the observation itself.

The observer effect in quantum mechanics does not necessarily involve a conscious observer. Any interaction with a measuring device can cause the collapse. In dyadic communication analysis, the "observer" is often a researcher or analyst, potentially influencing the communication through their presence or methods.

In the quantum world, the collapse is a fundamental change in the system's state because it generates a new state. In communication analysis, the change may be more subtle, with the presence of the researcher potentially leading to self-consciousness or altered behaviour.

¹² If the reader wants to delve deeper into this fascinating subject, the "double-slit" experiment of 1801, in which Thomas Young showed that particles behave differently when not observed than when observed, defining the so-called "interference pattern", is a must-read.

Furthermore, unlike quantum systems, humans have intentions and can communicate their thoughts and feelings to some degree; this makes dyadic communication analysis more complex than simply measuring a physical system.

In the end, maybe that observation directly changes the physical state, as maybe that observation changes the mental state and behaviour indirectly through expectation and social feedback. However, something will surely change, challenging the dyadic communication metric.

3. Conclusion

We began our journey analysing Leibniz's Monads: Leibniz's theory of monads posits that individual entities are self-contained and autonomous substances, each with its own unique properties and internal states. Monads do not interact directly with each other but reflect the entire universe from their perspective.

Then, drawing an analogy between monads and persons, we viewed individuals as self-contained entities with their thoughts, experiences, and perceptions. Like monads, individuals have their unique identity and perspective, shaping their interactions with others and the world around them.

The next logical step was to analyse dyadic communication, which involves the interaction between two individuals, each bringing their own subjective experiences and perspectives to interaction. Whereas Leibniz's monads are windowless and do not interact directly with each other

but seek to live in harmony, dyadic communication allows for the exchange of thoughts, ideas, and emotions between individuals.

Nevertheless, how can an exchange of thoughts be measured? Dyadic communication has an internal *caveat* in its difficulty of measurement: given monads' autonomy and windowless nature, it can be challenging to measure or observe them directly. Similarly, in dyadic communication, the subjective nature of individual experiences and perceptions makes it challenging to quantify or measure the interaction objectively. The complexity of human interaction and the dynamic interplay between individuals defies simple measurement or observation.

This difficulty is theoretically supported by two different but complementary effects: the Observer Effect in quantum mechanics and the Pygmalion effect: both the former and the latter refer to the phenomenon whereby the act of observation or measurement affects behaviour. Similarly, in dyadic communication, the presence of an observer or the awareness of being observed can influence the dynamics of the interaction, leading to different outcomes than when the interaction is not observed.

This interplay between the singularity of the Person, subjective experience, interaction, and observation underscores the complexity and richness of human communication and perception, transcending the boundaries of both metaphysics and quantum physics.

Meanwhile, the apparent limitations of monadic theory (not forgetting that it was instrumental as a response to Spinoza and as a tentative overthrow of Cartesian mind-body dualism) highlight the importance of shared frameworks, active interpretation, and the role of

social structures in facilitating understanding, since communication is also a process of interpreting internal representations, facilitated by shared cultural norms and social structures.

On the whole, although Leibniz's concept of monads and dyadic communication operates within different frameworks and contexts, they both offer insights into the complexities of individual identity, interaction, and perception. We can deepen our understanding of the dynamic nature of human communication and interpersonal relationships by exploring the parallels between these concepts.

After reflecting on the sociology of knowledge and its emphasis on the link between human ideas and their impact on society, technology, and science, the next logical step would be to continue the parallelism between quantum and sociology, with the emergence of the concept of "Superposition."

This principle states that quantum particles can exist in multiple states simultaneously until they are observed or measured, at which point they collapse into a new, single, definite state; in other words, superposition suggests that any two states can be combined as one to become a distinct state. However, how can the concept of "superposition" be applied to sociology? This article acknowledges the work of Steven Gerardi (2018), Professor Emeritus at New York City College of Technology, for his analysis of this issue.

According to him, this concept has profoundly impacted early classical sociological theory, giving rise to the new term 'Social Superposition,' a sociological theory in which two social states are combined and superimposed as one. However, when one social state is observed, a new and unique one emerges, and social change has occurred.

For example, in Mead, there are two concepts of self-development, the “I” and the “Me” (Social Superposition). According to Mead, the “I” is the unique sense of self, and the “ME” is the social concept of self. Once a person takes a role that involves seeing themselves from the perspective of others (Observer effect), he will become a new and unique self. At that moment, a new and socialised individual emerges.

Another exciting possibility for future research would be to consider the Autopoiesis of the Person in the context of monadic autonomy.

Autopoiesis (from Greek *αὐτο-* (auto-) 'self,' and *ποίησις* (poiesis) 'creation, production') refers to a system capable of producing and maintaining itself by creating its parts. It is usually applied in biology, describing how living systems self-organise and maintain their internal order.

Considering the studies of Maturana and Varela (1972), it could be used to explain how monads, as complex systems, could maintain a certain level of internal harmony. Different scholars, such as Niklas Luhmann, have already applied this concept in sociology with his Systems Theory, which Bob Jessop subsequently adapted in his studies of the capitalist state system. This biological perspective brings a new point of view to this topic, trying to answer the following question: Is the Person an autopoietic system?

It is to be hoped that this will be the subject of a future article.

A final word on philosophy's 'wet blanket' role, or rather the Philosophical Awareness and Methodological Challenges.

All this reflection about the inferences does not mean that no scientific measure can be taken in sociology.

The comparison between the Rosenthal "Pygmalion Effect" in psychology and the observer effect in physics applied to the metric of dyadic communication indeed underscores a crucial methodological challenge: an observed system is influenced by observation, and observation is influenced by the observer. This is a fact.

However, this does not imply that sociological measurements can never be scientific. Instead, it highlights the need for careful consideration and methodological rigour in sociological research¹³.

The role of philosophy in this context is not to act as a "wet blanket" but to raise awareness about the potential biases and influences that observation can introduce. By acknowledging these challenges, sociologists can develop more robust methodologies to account for and mitigate the observer effect through reflexivity (being constantly aware of their influence on the research process, recognizing and critically examining how researchers' presence and actions might affect their subjects and the data collected) from a personal level to the development of methodological tools like triangulation, double blinding and longitudinal studies.

The recognition that observation can influence behaviour does not undermine the scientific nature of sociological research. Instead, it calls for methodological sophistication and ethical awareness. Sociologists can produce valid, reliable, and scientifically sound results by designing studies that account for the observer effect. In other words, while the observer effect presents a methodological challenge in sociology, it does not preclude the possibility of scientific measurement.

¹³ See also the discussion between Léderer and Sómlai, A. „Léderer-tézis” bírálata: avagy a hazaküldött zongorahangoló esete, *REPLIKA* : 13-14 pp. 214-219. , 6 p. (1994)

Philosophy's role is to illuminate these challenges and guide researchers toward methods that enhance the integrity and credibility of their findings.

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ANNEX "A"

The Interstitial Liquid Analogy

If a person is a monad, where do they live? In a desert, in solitude, or in an organised context?

This article proposes that monads are an extremely well-studied and researched concept, as is the relationship between monads. However, there is a vacuum in philosophical reflection as to what is the medium in which monads live. For this reason - for didactic purposes - the analogy of the interstitial fluid is proposed, suggesting a comparison between society and the interstitial fluid itself.

As we can find well defined in Woodcock et al. (2024), interstitial fluid, also known as tissue fluid, is a thin, watery solution that fills the spaces between cells and tissues throughout the body. It accounts for about 20% of the body's total fluid and is essential for various vital functions. It is composed of water, electrolytes (such as sodium, potassium, and chloride), dissolved gases (like oxygen and carbon dioxide), nutrients (glucose, amino acids), and waste products (urea, carbon dioxide).

The Interstitial Fluid has several functions, such as:

1. **Transport of Nutrients and Waste Products:** Interstitial fluid is a medium for transporting nutrients from the bloodstream to cells and waste products from cells to the bloodstream. Nutrients like glucose and amino acids diffuse from capillaries into interstitial fluid and are then taken up by cells. Waste products like carbon dioxide and urea diffuse from cells into interstitial fluid and are then transported to capillaries to be removed from the body.

2. **Maintaining Cellular Environment:** Interstitial fluid helps maintain the proper osmotic balance and pH levels around cells, which is essential for their normal functioning. It also helps to cushion and protect cells from mechanical shock.
3. **Immune Function:** Interstitial fluid plays a role in the immune system by providing a medium for immune cells to move around and fight infections. It also contains antibodies and other immune factors that help to defend against pathogens.
4. **Regulation of Body Temperature:** Interstitial fluid plays a role in regulating body temperature by absorbing and releasing heat. When the body is too hot, sweat is produced from interstitial fluid to cool the body down. When the body is too cold, blood vessels constrict to conserve heat, and less interstitial fluid flows through the skin.

Society as Interstitial Fluid:

This article proposes that Society is the interstitial fluid surrounding and connecting monadic individuals. This element facilitates indirect communication and interaction and is essential for maintaining overall health and well-being. It is crucial in supporting individual functions, transporting nutrients or waste products, maintaining balance, and providing an immune system.

There is no single origin for this 'social fluid,' just as there is no single place in the body where interstitial fluid is produced. Its source can be found in:

Shared Norms and Values: These act like the solutes (dissolved substances) in the fluid. Shared beliefs, customs, and cultural understandings provide a framework for interaction and a sense of common ground between the monads (individuals). Like in Durkheim, collective conscience, social

solidarity, shared beliefs, and values are crucial for social integration and maintaining societal order and cohesion. Alternatively, the concept of the "social system" (1951) in Talcott Parson, where shared norms and values are essential for the stability and functioning of society.

Language and Communication: Language is a medium for exchanging information and ideas, similar to how nutrients and waste products are transported in interstitial fluid. Communication facilitates coordination and cooperation within the "social body:" This is similar to symbolic interactionism in Mead, which emphasised the importance of language and symbols in the development of the "Mind, Self and Society" (1934). Mead argued that communication through language is essential for social interaction and the formation of shared meanings.

Social Institutions: As pointed out by Meyer et al. (1997), institutions like family, education, and government establish structures and rules that guide behaviour and interaction. These elements co-exist within the societal fluid and can be seen as channels for the flow of the fluid, shaping how individuals connect.

Evolution of the Fluid: Just as the composition of interstitial fluid changes based on physiological needs, the societal fluid can evolve over time as norms, values, and communication methods change.

Distribution of the Fluid: Not all parts of society may be equally exposed to the "societal fluid." Marginalised groups or those on the fringes might have limited access to shared norms and communication channels. This concept is heavily present in the Conflict Theory, in the cultural and social capital gap as defined by Pierre Bourdieu (1986), or in the marginalisation by power imbalances from Habermas (1984).

Pathological state: As conflict theory teaches, societies can be full of conflict and power struggles. The societal fluid also needs to take these dynamics into account. Like an Oedema can be caused by various factors, such as increased capillary permeability or decreased oncotic pressure due to low protein levels, so in a conflict, we have parties with competing interests, such as political power, resources, and clashing, leading to instability. It can be resolved by negotiation or by fighting, just as oedema can be resolved or lead to chronic swelling.

Limitations of the Analogy:

Monads are philosophical constructs, while people are complex beings with emotions, intentions, and the ability to shape their environment. This paper acknowledges that this analogy, developed for didactical purposes, might oversimplify human interaction. However, despite such limitations, this analogy between monads, society, and interstitial fluid offers a creative way of thinking about how individuals interact within a larger social context.